

SCHOOL HEADS MORAL PRINCIPLES AND THE WORK MOTIVATION OF PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to investigate the effect of school head moral principles on the work motivation of secondary school teachers in Malvar District. This end was fulfilled by three objectives namely: to explore the existing status of teacher's morale in secondary schools, to assess the motives of the existing status of school head moral principles, and to examine the relationship between school head moral principles to work motivation of public secondary school teachers. This study was guided by motivation and leadership theories. The study applied quantitative and descriptive research approaches. This method enables the researchers to interpret the theoretical meaning of the findings and hypothesis development for further studies. The data were collected through questionnaires from 153 teachers administered in five secondary schools of Malvar District; Don Julio Leviste Memorial National High School, Malvar School of Arts and Trade MSAT, Santiago National High School, and San Isidro National High School. The study was conducted during the second quarter of the school year 2020-2021 in public schools. Researcher-made questionnaires will be used to generate data on school head moral principles and the work motivation of public secondary school teachers. The researcher made a survey questionnaire that is divided into six parts which are demographic profile, moral approaches, moral states, intrinsic motivation, extrinsic motivation, and validation. Generally, the findings revealed a strong positive relationship between the work motivation of the teachers from the school head moral principles. The study will aid in raising awareness among administrators of the importance of treating teachers fairly to improve teacher morale and academic performance in general.

Keywords: Moral Approaches, Moral States, Intrinsic Motivation and Extrinsic Motivation